

MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SQUEEZE CAST AZ91 Mg/Al₂O₃ METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, Al₂O₃/Mg metal matrix composites were fabricated with a variation of the applied pressure by the squeeze casting technique. Investigation on the squeeze cast microstructure and estimation of strength and fracture toughness were carried out for the squeeze cast composites. SEM in-situ fracture experiment was also performed to examine microcrack propagation in the composites. It is shown that the modification in preform preparation process improved microstructural features and mechanical properties of the squeeze cast composites.

I. INTRODUCTION

The limitation in mechanical properties and corrosion resistance have restricted the application of Mg alloys as engineering materials. However recent efforts for the development of Mg alloy matrix composites have shown possibilities for the expansion of the usage of Mg alloys for structural components. Advantageous properties of Mg matrix composites include high specific stiffness, high specific strength and small thermal expansion etc¹⁻³. Mg alloys matrix composites be strengthened not only by reinforcing but also by microstructural refining of Mg matrix with addition of a reinforcement.

Metal matrix composites have been fabricated on the routes of either powder metallurgy or casting processes. Although the former process provides better quality composites, the latter is more cost effective and thus more prospective for the manufacturing process of commercial metal matrix composites. Among casting techniques, the squeeze casting method has been used to develop high quality metal matrix composites⁴⁻⁶. Applied pressure during the squeeze casting make it possible to refine matrix microstructure and to increase reinforcement/matrix wettability, and thus to improve mechanical properties of metal matrix composites. In addition, the squeeze casting method is appropriate for mass production of near-net shape parts.

In this study, Mg/Al₂O₃ metal matrix composite were fabricated with a variation of applied pressure by the squeeze casting technique, and characterizations on the squeeze cast microstructure and mechanical properties were performed. Relationship between microstructure and mechanical properties has been studied.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

AZ91 HP Mg(Mg-8.9Al-0.7Zn-0.2Mn) and Al₂O₃ short fiber (crystallized with average dimensions of 3 μm in diameter and 200 μm in length, 97%Al₂O₃-3%SiO₂: Saffil RF grade) were used as matrix and reinforcement respectively for the fabrication of squeeze cast Mg/Al₂O₃ metal matrix composites. Preforms of reinforcement were prepared by employing the vacuum suction method. A mixture of Saffil fiber, 3% silica colloidal binder and 0.5% Latex organic binder was dispersed in distilled water and was sucked with vacuum. The volume fraction of Saffil short fiber was roughly controlled with vacuum suction pressure. Slurry of reinforcement was also degassed for evacuation of remaining gas bubble in preforms. Preforms were dried (at room temperature for 7 days, and at 100°C for 1 day in oven) and sintered (at 1,000°C for 3 hours). Squeeze casting was carried out by pouring molten Mg of 800°C into the sintered Al₂O₃ preform, which was preheated to 450°C and placed in the squeeze cast mold preheated to 450°C too, and then by applying pressure. In applying pressure, delay time and duration time were 7 and 60 seconds respectively. The applied pressure of 35, 55 and 75 MPa were chosen for squeeze casting. Optical and SEM microscopy study was carried out for the investigation of the solidification microstructures of the composites.

Three-point bend test for evaluating the flexural strength of the composites was carried out. Dimensions of three-point bending specimen were 2.4×25×60 mm and flexural strength was measured according to the specifications of ASTM D790. Plane-strain fracture toughness K_{IC} test was conducted to Chevron notched three-point bend-type specimen⁷⁻¹⁰, which satisfy ASTM thickness requirement (8×10×60 mm), and K_{IC} was calculated from the maximum load P_{max} of the load-displacement curve. In-situ SEM fracture test for directly observing the fracture process was conducted using a compact tension (CT) type loading stage¹¹⁻¹³. Dimensions of CT type specimen were 19×20 mm with a thickness of 0.3 mm in the grooved section and sharp notch (about 75μm radius) was introduced using an electro-discharge machine. At each loading step, the value of stress intensity factor could be also measured since the load applied to the specimen was monitored by a load cell (the maximum load : 20 Kg) which was connected to the X-Y recorder.

From this loading stage, apparent fracture toughness was estimated, for the comparison purpose, with the small and thin compact tension(CT) type specimen. Test and data interpretation procedures followed ASTM E399 specifications and the maximum load of the load-time curve was considered to be K_Q¹⁴, because such brittle materials as Mg matrix composites show little plastic behavior.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

III-1. SOLIDIFICATION MICROSTRUCTURE

Squeeze cast microstructures of unreinforced and Al₂O₃ reinforced Mg alloy with a variation

Figure 1. Microstructure of the squeeze cast AZ91 Mg reinforced with Al₂O₃. Applied pressure for squeeze casting : (a) 35 MPa, (b) 55 MPa and (c) 75 MPa.

Figure 2. Microstructure of the squeeze cast AZ91 Mg unreinforced. Applied pressure for squeeze casting : (a) 35 MPa, (b) 55 MPa and (c) 75 MPa.

of applied pressure are shown in Figure 1 and 2. Distribution of fibers is fairly uniform in AZ91/Al₂O₃ reinforced region. The preform deformation during the squeeze infiltration process reduced due to improvement of preform strength. The volume fraction slightly increased with increasing the applied pressure. Grain refinement of the unreinforced region is noticeable as the applied pressure is increased. Grain size of the reinforced and unreinforced region and volume fraction of the reinforced region were measured, and are summarized in Table 1. The grain size of the reinforced region is smaller than that of the

unreinforced region. In general, grains are refined in squeeze casting process. This grain refinement is achieved partly by the effective constitutional supercooling and partly by the dendrite arm breakage during squeezing of liquid melt¹⁵. It has been also reported that reinforcements play an important role in grain refinement of Al-SiC and Cu-Carbon fiber composites fabricated by the squeeze casting method¹⁶⁻¹⁹, since reinforcements provide heterogeneous nucleation sites due to the temperature difference between the fibers and molten metal.

Table 1. Grain size of the squeeze cast AZ91 Mg unreinforced and reinforced with Al₂O₃ short fibers, and volume fraction of Al₂O₃ reinforcement for the composites, fabricated with different applied pressure.

Applied pressure (MPa)	35		55		75	
	Composite	Matrix	composite	Matrix	Composite	Matrix
Grain Size (μm)	14	30	12	25	10	17
Volume Fraction of short fiber(%)	22	-	23	-	26	-

From microstructural examination of the squeeze cast Al₂O₃ composites fabricated in the present study, no cast defect has been observed and no fiber breakage was found up to high applied pressure.

III-2. STRENGTH AND IN-SITU FRACTURE BEHAVIOR

Three-point bending strength of the squeeze cast AZ91/Al₂O₃ composites are shown in Table 2. The bending strength for both reinforced and unreinforced region increased with increasing the applied pressure. The bending strength of reinforced region was higher than that of unreinforced region. The increasing trend of the bending strength of the composites with increasing the applied pressure might result from the volume fraction increment and matrix grain refinement.

Table 2. Three-point bending strength of the squeeze cast AZ91 Mg/Al₂O₃ composites.

Applied Pressure (MPa)	35		55		75	
	Composite	Matrix	Composite	Matrix	Composite	Matrix
Bending Strength (MPa)	357	282	426	355	457	398

Figure 3 is SEM micrographs showing fracture process ahead of a notch tip of a CT specimen made of the squeeze cast AZ91/Al₂O₃ composite fabricated with the applied pressure of 75MPa. Microcracks were formed by interfacial debonding between the matrix and fibers (Fig.3 (a)). The propagation of the main crack proceeded by the connection of

Figure 3. A series of SEM micrographs of the in-situ near notch tip fracture process for the squeeze cast AZ91/Al₂O₃ composite fabricated with 75 MPa, showing (a) microcrack formation at matrix/fiber interfaces, (b) crack propagation by the connection of interfacial microcracks and (c) local plastic deformation and failure of the Mg matrix between microcracks.

these microcracks in the direction normal to wedge loading (Fig.3 (b)). Local shear plastic deformation and failure of the Mg matrix in the region between microcracks were also found along the path of main crack propagation (Fig.3 (c)).

III-3. FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

Fracture toughness of the squeeze cast AZ91 Mg/Al₂O₃ composites was evaluated with Chevron notched bend specimen. Fracture toughness(K_{IC}) was calculated from the maximum load P_{max} using the following equation²⁰⁾,

$$K_{IC} = P_{max} Y_c(\alpha_o) / BW^{1/2}$$

where, $Y_c(\alpha_o) = 5.639 + 27.44\alpha_o + 18.93\alpha_o^2 - 43.42\alpha_o^3 + 338.9\alpha_o^4$

P_{max} = maximum load B = thickness

W = width α_o = a_o/W

a_o = initial effective crack length

Table 3. Fracture toughness of the squeeze cast AZ91/Al₂O₃ composites estimated with Chevron notched three-point bend type specimen.

Applied Pressure (MPa)	35	55	75
Chevron notch K _{IC} (MPam ^{1/2})	17.4	17.8	19.5

The results are shown in Table 3. Fracture toughness of the composites increased with increasing the squeeze cast pressure. Figure 4 shows load vs. displacement curves measured during bend tests of Chevron notched specimens. The maximum load P_{max} in the composites revealed higher with higher applied pressure in squeeze casting. The sudden drop in load after reaching P_{max} in the composite fabricated with 75 MPa could be an evidence of somewhat unstable crack growth occurred at the peak load⁷⁾.

Figure 4. Load-displacement curves of the squeeze cast AZ91/Al₂O₃ composites obtained from three-point bend tests with Chevron notched specimens.

Figure 5 shows SEM fractographs and EDX analysis of Chevron notched specimens of the squeeze cast AZ91 Mg/Al₂O₃ composites. A number of short fibers distributed irregularly are to be pulled out, and a few ductile dimpled regions which are thought to be caused by the Mg alloy matrix were also detected. Any noticeable difference was not found in fractography between the composites. However, Mg matrix remnant attached on the fiber surfaces detached during fracturing process (indicated with arrow and analyzed by EDX in Figure 5) might be more frequently found with increased applied pressure in squeeze casting.

Fracture toughness was also measured in the in-situ SEM wedge loading stage with small and thin CT specimen for the squeeze cast AZ91 Mg/Al₂O₃ composites. The results of apparent fracture toughness(K_Q) of the composites were 14.2 for 35 MPa and 17.5 for 75 MPa. We obtained comparable values in fracture toughness between Chevron notched specimens (Table 3) and small size CT specimens, even though both measurement might be preliminary measurement methods of fracture toughness for the Mg matrix composites under study.

Figure 5. SEM fractographs of Chevron notched fracture toughness test specimens of squeeze cast AZ91 Mg/Al₂O₃ composites fabricated with (a) 35, (b) 55 and (c) 75 MPa. (d) is EDX analysis of A and B part.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

1. Modification in the fabrication process such as using silica-Latex mixture binder and adapting preform sintering improved properties of Al₂O₃ reinforcement preform and thus resulted in the improvement of microstructure and mechanical properties of the squeeze cast AZ91 Mg/Al₂O₃ composites.
2. Microstructure of the squeeze cast AZ91 Mg/Al₂O₃ composites fabricated in this study revealed fairly uniform distribution of Al₂O₃ short fibers. Grain size of Mg matrix decreased and volume fraction of Al₂O₃ increased with increasing applied pressure.
3. Fracture toughness and bending strength of the composites increased as the applied pressure for the squeeze casting increased up to 75 MPa. Fracture toughness of the squeeze cast AZ91 Mg/Al₂O₃ composites were confirmed by two experimental methods simultaneously, Chevron notched three point bend test and in-situ SEM fracture test with CT wedge loading stage. In-situ SEM observation for the fracture process revealed microcrack formation mainly by matrix/fiber interface debonding. No evidence of reinforcement fiber damage in the composites fabricated with up to 75 MPa was found in microstructural and in-situ SEM observation.

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